

Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)

Project: Automated Metadata Generation and Semantic Tagging Investigation
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Project Student: Ashley Owen Doel

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1 Project Details

Project Name	Automated Metadata Generation and Semantic Tagging Investigation
Project Dates	27th June - 4th September 2024

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1.3 Project Description

The project focused on evaluating and comparing various software libraries for extracting metadata from chemistry research papers. The researcher identified six libraries that could extract both generic information, such as paper titles and authors, and domain-specific metadata, like chemical compounds and formulas. To test the libraries, a custom pipeline was developed, which involved scraping papers from Elsevier and the Royal Society of Chemistry, then processing them through the selected libraries. The performance of each library was assessed by comparing the extracted metadata to known ground truth data and to the other libraries. The project revealed that while some tools performed well with generic metadata, challenges remained with domain-specific extraction, format dependencies, and runtime efficiency.

2 Lay Summary

This project focused on developing and evaluating tools for extracting important information, known as metadata, from scientific papers in the field of chemistry. The work involved identifying and testing six different software libraries that can automatically pull out details like the title, authors, journal, and chemical data from research articles.

To achieve this, a custom testing pipeline was created, which involved gathering papers from major publishers like Elsevier and the Royal Society of Chemistry. The selected libraries used techniques like text analysis and machine learning to extract both general information (such as the paper's title) and specialized chemical data (like compound names). The results showed that while some tools performed well in extracting basic information, others struggled with more complex chemical terms, and some tools were slow or relied on specific file formats.

This project highlights both the potential and the limitations of current tools in helping researchers quickly gather useful data from scientific literature, paving the way for future improvements in this field.

3 Introduction

Metadata in literature is broadly defined, often summarized by the phrase "data about data" [1], a description that is referenced in at least 15 different ISO standards [2]. More precise definitions are offered by scholars such as Haslhofer and Klas, who describe metadata as "machine-processable data" used to characterize "resources, digital or non-digital" [3]. Additionally, Ulrich et al. propose that metadata comprises three dimensions: structural, descriptive, and administrative [4]. At its core, metadata is information about something, and it has played a crucial role in shaping the academic data landscape over the past two decades. With metadata, digital repositories enable users to efficiently query and filter academic papers [5], enhancing the speed and breadth of research capabilities compared to traditional methods [6]. The benefits of being able to search and re-use shared data cannot be overstated; for instance, Rodrigo et al. highlight how the re-use of older data has facilitated new experiments, including analyses showing that the Higgs Boson could have been confirmed using data from the LEP (Large Electron-Positron Collider) [5]. However, creating useful metadata can be challenging, as manual tagging is time-consuming and prone to human error. Moreover, generating accurate metadata may require domain-specific expertise or additional contextual information [4], necessitating further development and refinement.

In line with the typical approach in computer science, digital automation has been introduced to address these challenges. Metadata extractors are seen as an ideal solution for automating metadata generation. These tools operate on a straightforward functional model: given a digital object, such as a PDF of a paper, the extractor returns all the relevant metadata it can identify. Ideally, the extractor would provide comprehensive metadata about the object, but this is often an unrealistic expectation. For instance, a document might not contain all the necessary information, such as its publication details, and thus, that data cannot be extracted. Additionally, the desired metadata may vary depending on the audience. Research by Skluzacek, Chard, and Foster indicates that users may have differing opinions on the appropriate values for certain metadata tags [7]. Consequently, it is common practice to design extractors with a specific scope tailored to the needs of a particular audience.

Currently, research on metadata extraction tools specifically designed for physical chemistry literature is sparse. Most existing work has focused on developing general-purpose metadata extractors that can be applied across multiple domains, such as Xtract [7] and CERMINE [8]. Nonetheless, several open-source tools for chemical tagging and extraction have been developed, offering a promising direction for creating a metadata extraction tool specialized in chemical content. Additionally, the difficulties encountered in adapting these tools for metadata extraction may reveal potential issues in the design of future tools, underscoring the need for more specialized solutions.

3.1 Research Problem

This paper explores the development of a metadata generation tool tailored specifically for physical chemistry literature, leveraging existing open-source libraries. The process involves identifying suitable libraries that can be integrated to create effective extractors, followed by the construction of a robust testing environment to evaluate the performance of these extractors on various chemistry papers, with careful consideration of field and topic-specific variables. Consequently, the objectives of this study are as follows:

1. Identify suitable open-source libraries.
2. Design and implement a testing pipeline that provides appropriate papers, to extractors constructed from the identified libraries, and facilitates a comparative analysis of the extractor outcomes.
3. Assess the effectiveness of each extractor based on its underlying technology, with particular emphasis on its ability to generate valuable metadata.

3.2 Supplementary Background Information

To provide readers with the necessary understanding of the technologies discussed later in this paper, this section offers supplementary background information on extractors and scrapers. This section should be skipped by readers with prior experience of the topics.

3.2.1 Extractors

Building on the earlier definition, extractors can be categorized based on their extraction methodologies into three main types:

- **Parser extractors** operate by leveraging their understanding of an object’s structure, either by searching for specific keywords or by locating particular fields within a markup language. This approach is the most straightforward but requires the digital object to adhere to a specific structure, which may not always be practical.
- **Natural language processing (NLP) extractors** analyze human-readable text to identify sentiment and meaning, tagging various parts of the text according to predefined classes. These tags can then be used to generate metadata. For example, in their work, Mao, Garijo, and Fakhraei used SoMEF to tag sections of GitHub README files as description, installation, invocation, or citation [9]. The tagged content was then parsed into a JSON output, which was used to generate corresponding metadata for each README file.
- **Computer vision extractors** employ image classification techniques to analyze and interpret visual content, identifying specific characteristics within images. For instance, Karnani et al. utilized object detection on digital biological specimens to generate metadata regarding the presence of elements such as fish, eyes, and rulers [10].

It is important to note that the development of NLP and computer vision extractors is often more complex and challenging compared to parsers. These extractors frequently rely on machine learning models, such as Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which require extensive data preparation, careful tuning, and significant time for training and execution. Although parsers do not incur these costs, the burden can be mitigated through the reuse of pre-trained machine learning extractors.

3.2.2 Scrapers

To efficiently aggregate online data, web scrapers are commonly used to extract information from web servers. Converting unstructured web data, originally intended for human consumption, into a machine-readable format like JSON involves the use of page scrapers. These scrapers typically employ one of two methods: sending low-level HTTP requests and parsing the resulting responses, or running a full web browser to interact with and parse the live DOM. Similar to parser extractors, this process relies on predefined knowledge of the website's structure and is limited in its ability to handle unexpected changes.

When a web server provides an API, an API scraper can be utilized, functioning similarly to HTTP-based scraping. Instead of retrieving web pages via GET requests, the scraper interacts with specific endpoints, often using parameters like query terms. These services are typically governed by licensing agreements and require the use of an API key for each request.

Another method, semantic web scraping, exists but will not be discussed further as it was not used in this project.

Web scraping, which has recently gained prominence, is a powerful tool for collecting large volumes of data from online sources. It has found significant applications in business intelligence and artificial intelligence [11]. However, this technique raises legal and ethical concerns. For example, Facebook's successful lawsuit against Power.com highlighted issues of copyright infringement, as Power.com's scraper published data from fully downloaded pages without authorization [12]. Therefore, careful consideration must be given to the content and context of the data being scraped, particularly when it involves personal information that may not have been explicitly provided for such use.

4 Methodology

4.1 Methodology intro

To fulfil the three objects, as outline in 3.1, two stages were employed and performed sequentially. Firstly, libraries were identified to be tested as candidate extractors, following they fulfilled suitable criterion. Next, the libraries would be developed into extractors, and compared against each other on papers generated from web scraping [Elsevier APIs](#) and the RSC's (Royal Society of Chemistry) [open access published journals](#).

4.2 Identifying Libraries

The identification of libraries suitable for metadata extraction from chemistry literature involved a systematic approach combining functional and administrative criteria. Functionally, the focus was on tools with broad compatibility, with a preference for Python libraries due to their widespread use in PSDI. The selected libraries needed to process raw text, PDFs, or XML files, and generate either generic ,domain-specific or both types of metadata. From an administrative perspective, the selection focused on free, open-source libraries released post-2010, ensuring the inclusion of current and actively maintained projects. Furthermore, to avoid niche and under-documented solutions, only libraries with documented mentions in academic literature or those with dedicated research papers were considered. The search for relevant projects involved utilizing paper search engines from the Southampton Library and Google Scholar with keywords such as "automated metadata generation," "metadata extraction," and "chemical tagging." Additionally, Research Rabbit was employed to trace the references and citations of identified papers, and peer recommendations were also incorporated into the search process, ensuring a comprehensive survey of available resources.

4.3 Testing pipeline

To effectively assess the extraction potential of various libraries, a testing pipeline was developed. This pipeline was designed to fulfill the following objectives:

- Providing suitable papers from chemistry journals on specific topics for the extractors to analyze.
- Implementing wrappers for libraries that do not independently offer metadata extraction capabilities, such as parsing results from a semantic tagging tool, ensuring all libraries are treated equally as extractors.
- Facilitating clear comparison tools for different metadata fields, accommodating a range of data types and comparison scenarios.

The resulting pipeline consists of several key components, as can be seen in figure 1. Initially, a scraper class is employed to generate a collection of papers along with associated metadata. This metadata serves as the ground truth, although it may be limited depending on the scraper's capabilities. The generated papers and metadata are then passed to a PaperReader class, which creates a paper object and a corresponding metadata object. The paper object is subsequently provided to the extractor classes, each wrapper on libraries, which each returns its own instance of metadata. Finally, the extracted metadata objects are compared against the ground truth using a Comparator class. The following sections will provide a detailed discussion of the three main components: the scrapers, the extractor classes, and comparing metadata.

Figure 1: Pipeline for testing extractors

4.3.1 Scrapers

Given the time constraints of this project, only two publisher-specific scrapers were developed: one for Elsevier and one for the Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC). Both are prominent publishers of chemistry journals with open access papers. While limiting the scope to these two publishers does constrain the range of potential formatting issues encountered, this decision was necessary to maintain focus on the extraction and evaluation processes. Future research should aim to broaden the range of publishers to address a wider variety of formatting challenges.

Before developing the web scrapers, careful consideration was given to legal and ethical issues related to the data. The content scraped was restricted to open access papers and included minimal personal information—specifically, the authors’ names. Given the open access nature of the content, there were no significant legal or ethical concerns, and approval from an ethics committee was not required.

Functionally, the RSC scraper operates by performing iterative searches through GET requests to URLs in the format [https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlehtml/\\$year/\\$journal_code/\\$id](https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlehtml/$year/$journal_code/$id). The URL includes parameters for the year, journal code, and paper ID, which allows for searches across the entire timeline of the journal. Each page is scraped for available metadata, including links to additional papers from the same journal and the URL for downloading the PDF version of the paper. In contrast, the Elsevier scraper utilizes the ScienceDirect APIs, specifically the [Search API V2](#), the [Article Metadata API](#), and the [Article \(Full Text\) Retrieval API](#). This scraper retrieves articles based on query terms, such as journal names, and can download open access papers along with their associated metadata. This process is more formalized, following directions from a provided API instead of implementing an extractor to the current page format. As a result, the RSC scraper may be more susceptible to failures due to unannounced changes in formatting, whereas the Elsevier scraper benefits from the more stable and published updates of Elsevier’s APIs.

4.3.2 Extractors

In the testing pipeline, extractors refer to the individual libraries wrapped to perform an extraction method that, given the location of a file, returns any extracted metadata. This interface facilitates the integration of a diverse range of libraries, enhancing modularity. Some libraries are designed to operate solely on raw text and require the use of a PDF-to-text converter. For the experiment, [PyMuPDF.fitz](#), [pdftotext](#), and [pdfBox](#) were employed to provide a variety of established solutions, ensuring that the libraries were minimally constrained by this factor. Additionally, the model accommodated both Python and Java-based libraries by using the [JPype](#) library ([JPype](#)) to enable Java code execution within Python. This approach ensured that all libraries utilized the same metadata and comparator classes, thereby facilitating fair and

consistent results.

4.3.3 Comparing Metadata

In this study, metadata is internally represented as two lists of entries, categorized as either valid or invalid. Each metadata entry consists of a key-value pairing. The validity of an entry is determined by its name being included in the predefined schema for valid metadata entries, as well as the data type matching the schema specification. This schema was designed to restrict the range of metadata properties evaluated by extractors, containing only thirteen valid metadata fields. The data types of these entries correspond to the structure of the metadata, which may consist of: an atom (stored as a string), a set of atoms, or a frequency set of atoms (formally defined as a set of tuples containing the atom and its frequency). The complete schema specification is illustrated in Figure 1. Additionally, the schema incorporates an error boundary, which is employed by the comparator class to accommodate minor mistakes in parsed text, such as the removal of special characters or the addition of spaces.

Name	Data Type	Classification	Error Boundary
Paper Title	Atomic	Generic	N/A
Authors	Set	Generic	5%
DOI	Atomic	Generic	N/A
Language	Atomic	Generic	N/A
Publish Date	Atomic	Generic	N/A
Journal Title	Atomic	Generic	N/A
Subject	Set	Domain	5%
Keywords	Set	Domain	5%
Compounds	Set	Domain	0%
Formulas	Set	Domain	0%
Chemical Terms	Set	Domain	0%
Smiles	Set	Domain	0%

Table 1: Valid Metadata Entry Schema

The comparator compares entries with matching keys and employs distinct techniques based on the data type of the metadata:

- **Atomic Comparison** is carried out using the [FuzzyWuzzy](#) library, which implements the Levenshtein distance [13], a widely used metric for string similarity. This method returns a percentage representing the degree of similarity between two strings.
- **Set Comparison** is conducted using the Jaccard distance [14], a metric that measures similarity between finite sets. Prior to this calculation, atomic comparison is applied to the set members, utilizing the error boundary to merge similar set entries. This process yields a percentage that reflects the similarity between two sets of metadata entries.

- **Frequency Set Comparison** follows the same procedure as set comparison, with pre-processing to convert tuples into separate instances based on frequency. The outcome is a percentage similarity that takes into account the frequency of each atom.

The results of these comparisons can be used to assess whether metadata matches the ground truth obtained through web scraping. Furthermore, these results are valuable for identifying discrepancies between extractors in fields without an established ground truth, enabling the identification of outlier fields that may require further manual investigation.

5 Results

5.1 Library Identification

Through the identification process, outlined in section 4.2, six libraries were identified, fulfilling the first objective from the paper’s research problem. These papers were believed to provide a diverse range of generic and domain metadata extracting capabilities, utilizing parsers, NLP and one using computer vision techniques. A summary of these properties and technologies can be seen in table 2.

Name	Language	Metadata Types	Classification	Machine Learning Models
Apache Tika	Java	Generic	Parser	N/A
PDF Miner	Python	Generic	Parser	N/A
PDF Data Extractor [15]	Python	Generic	Parser	N/A
Chemical Tagger [16]	Java	Domain	NLP	OSCAR4 [17]
Chem Data Extractor 2 [18]	Python	Generic and Domain	Parser and NLP	SciBERT model [19] with additional Conditional Random Fields (CRF).
OpenChemIE [20]	Python	Domain	NLP and Vision	ChemNER [21] for semantic tagging and MolScribe [22] for chemical image translation.

Table 2: Identified Potential Extractor Libraries

Three generic parser tools have been identified as useful for extracting data from chemistry literature. Apache Tika, a Java-based parser toolkit, was identified for its content detection and analysis capabilities across a wide range of file formats. Although its versatility in handling multiple formats [23] is not particularly beneficial for this PDF-focused study, Tika stands out as highly expandable, with community-developed parsers and tooling designed for creating custom parsers. This flexibility could offer advantages in developing tailored solutions for specific academic paper formats. However, Tika’s support for parsing academic PDFs remains limited, reducing its immediate usefulness in this context.

PDF Miner, a commonly used Python library for reading data from PDFs, was also identified. While not directly better than Tika, PDF Miner offers specific features for accessing metadata fields within PDF files, making it relevant for this study’s focus on PDF content extraction. Additionally, PDFDataExtractor, developed by Zhu and Cole, builds upon PDF Miner to enhance chemistry-specific information extraction. Designed as a plugin for ChemDataExtractor, it uses templates based on six key chemistry papers to improve metadata extraction from scientific PDFs [15].

The identification process also revealed three semantic tagging tools that can be utilized to generate metadata on the chemical terminology present in literature.

Chemical Tagger is a semantic text mining tool designed to identify and tag chemical entities

within text [16]. It employs OSCAR4 for chemical entity recognition, which integrates regular expressions, a Naive Bayes classifier, and the Maximum Entropy Markov Model (MEMM) to achieve accurate recognition of chemical entities [17]. However, Chemical Tagger is not a PDF reader; it operates by converting text into parse trees, necessitating an additional extractor wrapper to first convert PDFs to raw text before semantic tagging can occur.

ChemDataExtractor2 is a toolkit specifically developed for extracting chemical information from various literature formats, including PDFs, plain text, Elsevier XML, and RSC HTML [18]. It supports the extraction of both generic metadata and chemical terms. For metadata extraction, ChemDataExtractor2 utilizes parsers such as pdfminer and lxml. For chemical terms, it leverages the SciBERT model [19] enhanced with an additional Conditional Random Fields (CRF) layer, providing robust performance in extracting chemical information from scientific texts.

OpenChemIE is a comprehensive toolkit designed to extract chemical information from literature, encompassing both figures and text [20]. It integrates several tools and classifiers: PDFtoText for text extraction from PDFs, MolScribe for figure extraction [22], ChemNer for named entity recognition in text [21], and ChemRxnExtractor for reaction extraction [24]. This toolkit effectively combines various components to facilitate a broad spectrum of chemical information extraction from scientific documents.

5.2 Testing and Evaluation

Due to the study’s limited timeframe, papers were tested using a single sample set from each scraper. For RSC, the sample comprised papers from CrystEngComm Issue 9, 2008, while for Elsevier, the search results were based on the term "Aspirin." It is acknowledged that future research, with extended resources, should significantly enhance coverage and control across various topics. By evaluating the return values for metadata fields against the limited ground truth metadata and comparing them with each other to assess group sentiment, the study was able to determine which metadata fields the extractors could successfully generate. The results are presented in Table 3.

Extractor	Paper Title	Authors	DOI	Language	Publish Date	Journal Title	Subject	Keywords	Compounds	Formulas	Chemical Terms	Smiles
Tika	Els	Els	Els	Els	Els	Els
PDFMiner	Bth	Bth	Bth	.	Els	.	.	Bth
PDFDataExtractor	Bth	Rsc	Bth	.	Rsc	.	.	Bth
ChemicalTagger	Bth	Bth	.	.	.
ChemDataExtractor	Els	Bth	Bth	Bth	.	Bth	.	.	.	Bth	Bth	.
OpenChemIE	Bth	Bth	Bth	Bth	Bth

Table 3: Results of which extractors return which metadata fields.
 Key: *Els=Elsevier Only, Rsc=RSC Only, Bth=Both Journals*

The overall quality of generic metadata fields identified was consistently high, with values either being accurately identified or absent. However, this was not the case for domain-specific metadata. Through the use of a comparator to assess similarity and manual inspection, it became apparent that ChemicalTagger, and to a lesser extent ChemDataExtractor, were producing erroneous tags. For example, "acids,7" was incorrectly labeled as a compound rather than as "acid" in the context of chemical terminology. The first issue is attributed to the persistent challenges associated with PDF-to-text converters, which remain problematic despite various attempts to use different converters. This difficulty arises from the inherent complexities of PDF formatting, a topic outside the scope of this study but important to acknowledge. The second issue pertains to limitations in differentiating between compounds and chemical terms. It is believed that OpenChemIE effectively addressed this problem by annotating text under one of seven types, which closely aligned with the desired metadata fields.

During testing, issues were encountered with the runtime of two extractors. It should be noted that these tests were conducted on a Mac M3 Pro with 18 GB of RAM, a relatively high-performance laptop. OpenChemIE required 7-10 minutes per paper, while ChemDataExtractor2 took 2-3 minutes. Although these runtime issues were inconvenient during development, the primary concern is the potential cost implications for future scaling of these technologies, particularly since OpenChemIE, despite being the slowest, provides the most accurate domain-specific metadata.

Additionally, testing revealed that multiple formats of scraped papers were necessary, particularly for ChemDataExtractor2. For example, if an HTML version was not available for RSC papers or an XML version for Elsevier papers, no generic metadata would be returned. This is due to the extractors' reliance on specific parsers designed for these formats, with the PDF parser only converting PDFs to text without generating metadata, and subsequently running chemical tagging features. This highlights a significant issue with parsers' dependence on specific formats.

Finally, it was observed that no extractor was able to retrieve the subject of papers. This is a notable limitation, as the ability to classify papers by subject would be highly valuable. This area is clearly a target for future research and development.

6 Conclusions & Future Work

6.1 Conclusion intro

In summary, the evaluation of various libraries for metadata extraction from chemistry literature has provided valuable insights into the current capabilities and limitations of these tools. The results indicate that while significant progress has been made, particularly in extracting generic metadata through parsers, challenges remain in addressing domain-specific metadata and adapting to format changes.

6.2 Future Work

The study highlighted a notable trend towards a combination of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Computer Vision (CV) techniques in metadata extraction tools. Libraries like OpenChemIE are already integrating these approaches to improve the extraction of chemical information from both text and figures. This hybrid approach shows promise in enhancing the accuracy and comprehensiveness of metadata extraction. However, further validation is needed to confirm the effectiveness of these combined methods and to ensure that they provide reliable and consistent results across diverse datasets.

For generic metadata, parsers have proven to be effective tools. Libraries such as Apache Tika and PDFMiner excel in extracting fundamental metadata fields like titles, authors, and DOIs from PDFs. However, these tools face limitations when it comes to handling structural changes in documents. The rigid nature of current parsing models makes them vulnerable to variations in document format, which can result in incomplete or inaccurate metadata extraction. Future research should explore the potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) to address these issues. LLMs, with their ability to understand and adapt to diverse text structures, could offer a more flexible and robust solution to overcoming the limitations of traditional parsers.

The future of metadata extraction in chemistry literature is likely to see a shift towards Python-based libraries. The trend away from Java projects, such as OSCAR4, towards Python-based solutions reflects the growing popularity and flexibility of Python in the data science community. Python libraries offer a more modern and accessible environment for developing and integrating advanced metadata extraction tools, making them a preferred choice for future developments.

One area that remains underexplored is the automatic determination of paper topics. Although OpenChemIE is making strides in this direction, there is still much work to be done to develop effective methods for categorizing scientific papers by subject. Future research should focus on improving topic determination techniques, potentially through enhanced machine learning models or more sophisticated NLP approaches, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the content and relevance of scientific papers.

Lastly, the study underscores the importance of using multiple extractors for specific tasks. No single tool demonstrated the capability to cover all metadata fields comprehensively. Combining different extractors allows for a more robust and accurate metadata extraction process, leveraging the strengths of each tool. For instance, while one extractor might excel at parsing generic metadata, another might be specialized in extracting domain-specific information. Utilizing multiple extractors ensures that a broader range of metadata can be captured, improving the overall quality and completeness of the extracted data.

6.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, while the current tools for metadata extraction have made significant advances, there is ample room for improvement. Future work should focus on integrating machine learning techniques into existing tools, exploring the potential of LLMs to overcome parsing limitations, and shifting towards Python-based solutions. Additionally, addressing the challenge of topic determination and employing multiple extractors for specific tasks will be crucial for advancing metadata extraction capabilities and enhancing the utility of these tools in the scientific literature domain.

7 Outputs, Data & Software Links

For the project and internship, two specific outputs were produced: a GitHub repository containing all source code for experiments, tutorials, and investigations, and a poster presented at the University of Southampton Undergraduate Summer Research Interns Poster Presentation. The private GitHub repository has been shared with Dr. Samantha Pearman-Kanza. Additionally, the poster can be found in the appendices.

The GitHub repository includes the work for this paper, which is located in the folder titled "main." This folder contains a README file, a setup bash file for configuring the Python 3.7 conda environment, and three primary folders, along with additional setup files. The folders serve the following purposes:

- The **Python** folder houses the Python source code, which constitutes the main body of work. It includes notebooks to run the experiments and classes for extractors, scrapers, papers/metadata, and utility functions, such as a factory for Java classes in Python.
- The **Java** folder contains the Java source code, which serves as the back-end for the Tika and ChemicalTagger extractors. To make these extractors runnable within the main Python project, the workspace must be compiled into a shaded jar file, executable via the package bash file.
- The **papers** folder serves as the storage location for all papers collected by the scraper classes in the Python library. These papers are organized in a manner that allows access by the PaperReader Python class.

It is noteworthy that the poster accompanying this paper, based on the aforementioned work, was awarded second place at the Southampton Undergraduate Summer Research Interns Poster Presentation.

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Limitations with Metadata Extraction for Chemistry Literature

Ashley Doel, Samantha Pearman-Kanza

An investigation into Automated Metadata Generation and Semantic Tagging

[1]

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PAPER

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Hydrogen bonding patterns in a series of 1-arylcycloalkanecarboxamides†

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2. Semantic Tagging

Through Named Entity Recognition (NER), we can identify entities such as chemical terms, compounds, and formulas. This identification process can be enhanced using formalized ontologies, which provide structured vocabularies and relationships.

For example, ChemicalTagger [2] utilizes OSCAR4, which combines regular expressions, a Naive Bayes classifier, and the Maximum Entropy Markov Model (MEMM) to accurately recognize chemical entities. ChemDataExtractor2 [3] employs the SciBERT model with an additional Conditional Random Fields (CRF) layer, offering robust performance in extracting chemical information from scientific texts. OpenChemIE [4], as part of its multi-modular framework, uses ChemNER, leveraging flexible knowledge-based (KB) matching and ontology-guided multi-type disambiguation to identify chemical entities.

Each approach progressively enhances the accuracy and comprehensiveness of semantic tagging, but challenges remain in handling ambiguous terms, context-specific meanings, and the integration of disparate data sources.

3. Computer Vision

As part of OpenChemIE's multi-modular design, the system uses MolScribe to convert molecular images into graph structures and then into SMILES strings. It employs an autoregressive decoder for atom prediction and a feed-forward model for bond prediction. This automation enhances the extraction of chemical metadata from visual data, improving the handling of graphical content in scientific literature.

Converting images into SMILES strings allows for further referencing of the chemical, though current challenges exist in linking wildcard patterns. This advancement in image recognition techniques provides a more integrated understanding of chemical information.

1. Generic Parsers

Generic parsers extract various types of metadata, including descriptive (title, author), structural (file type), and administrative (creation date). They leverage predefined file formats to efficiently extract information across different document types. Apache Tika, for instance, provides a versatile set of parsing tools capable of handling a wide range of file formats to retrieve metadata and text content. This approach is advantageous for its broad applicability and ease of use, allowing for quick processing of diverse files.

However, reliance on predefined formats can lead to challenges with unstructured or highly specialized content, resulting in potential gaps in metadata extraction.

Results and discussion

Crystallographic descriptions of the structures of 1-arylcycloalkanecarboxamides 1–5

Table 1 provides crystallographic details for compounds 1–5. The atomic numbering scheme for all five compounds is given in Fig. 1, which also shows the contents of the asymmetric unit in each case. The distances and angles within the five compounds reported are generally as expected.¹⁵ In all five structures, hydrogen bonds (summarised in Table 2) play a major part in controlling the supramolecular assembly of the molecules. In describing the hydrogen-bonding patterns in the five carboxamide structures reported in this study, we shall use unitary (N_1) and binary (N_2) graph set (GS) analysis.¹⁶ All structures have simple N–H...O hydrogen bonds; and, as expected, the primary hydrogen-bonded motif between molecules (Scheme 1) is a cyclic dimer [Synthon 1, $R_2^2(8)$]. In distinguishing between the two H atoms on the primary amide group, we shall follow the procedure of Desiraju⁵ in labelling the N–H atom *syn* to the carbonyl group (*i.e.*, the N–H atom involved in the formation of the cyclic dimer) as 'H₁' and the

- 1 R = H, n = 0
- 2 R = H, n = 1
- 3 R = F, n = 1
- 4 R = Cl, n = 1
- 5 R = Br, n = 1

Scheme 1 Structures of compounds 1–5, showing the hydrogen-bonded dimeric motif.

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5. Future Work

- Continue multi-modular multi-tooled designs, utilising classifiers in a tree-like structure, refining on each task
- Utilise LLMs/ML for generic metadata extracting - step away from curating a library of parsers
- Determining topic/consensus of papers

4. Experiment Pipeline

Web Scraper

- Elsevier
- RSC

Extractor

- Chemical Tagger
- Apache Tika
- CDE2
- OpenChemIE
- PdfDataExtractor
- PDFMiner

Comparator

University of Southampton

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

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